

A Preliminary Note on the Homology of BeF_4^{2-} and SO_4^{2-} Ions from Chemical, Structural and Crystallographic Points of View.

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Complex salts are generally divided according to their degree of stability into three classes, *viz.*,

(1) Perfect complexes as are exhibited by the less electropositive elements such as Pt, Co, Rh, Ir, etc., which are not at all dissociated into their constituents.

(2) Imperfect complexes, as shown by chromium, which partially dissociate.

(3) The double salts which undergo complete dissociation in aqueous solution, *e.g.*, 2KCl , SnCl_4 .

Such a classification of the complex ions actually presents serious difficulties on account of the transition which leads us insensibly from perfect complex ions to complex ions disintegrating in solution in such a way that the analytical characters cease to be the discriminating guide. In such cases the analogy cannot be searched for in the properties of the solution. It is therefore to the properties of the solid salts that recourse is to be taken for establishing the analogy. The similarity of crystalline form is of course one of the most valuable properties for consideration. Such an analogy may, however, be accidental. Several concordant presumptions are necessary for establishing the analogy. Amongst the necessary coincidences the identity of type is one of the essentials. Simple analogy of formula alone is of no value. If the compounds of analogous formulae are isomorphous in appearance it remains still to be assured that the conditions of "real" isomorphism are satisfied. The word "real" implies an analogy much more profound than that of simple exterior form. One of the characters of real isomorphism is the formation of mixed crystals, which can at least within certain limits, admit of infinite compositions. The crystallisation in all proportions is a particular and extreme case of the preceding. When this character accompanies an absolute identity of form, the isomorphism is perfect. But this conception has its limitations. In fact

the crystals of two isomorphous salts are never rigorously identical, the corresponding angles present always slight differences. That isomorphism reveals most profound chemical analogies is best exemplified by the family of the rare earths. Their salts of the same type have always the same crystalline form and they form mixed crystals in all proportions.

It is to be assumed that there are not only homologous elements but there are also homologous radicles. A very well-known example is furnished by ammonium and potassium ions. When certain elements or radicles can be substituted totally or partially in a variety of salts without disturbing the conditions for "real" isomorphism, the chemical homology of these elements or radicles remains indisputable.

One of the essential conditions of syncrystallisation of two perfectly isomorphous crystals is the quasi-equality of molecular volumes.

A search for literature about the double fluorides of beryllium reveals the existence of salts of the type MF , BeF_2 and $2MF$, BeF_2 (where $M=K, Na$ or Am). Up till now no investigation has been carried out to prove whether they form true double salts or constitute a complex ion. It has been found that on adding ammonia to a moderately concentrated solution of potassium beryllium fluoride ($2KF, BeF_2$), beryllium is only partially precipitated. Moreover, with a very concentrated solution of ammonium beryllium fluoride ($2NH_4F, BeF_2$, which is much more soluble than the potassium salt) the precipitation with ammonia cannot be effected and the precipitate of beryllium hydroxide can be made to appear on dilution of the ammoniacal solution. These observations amply justify the assumption that beryllium in solutions of these double fluoride is a constituent of a complex ion. This was definitely proved by a transport experiment. On electrolysing a concentrated solution of potassium beryllium fluoride a gradual and marked increase in the concentration of beryllium at the anode was observed although part of the beryllium was precipitated as hydroxide at the cathode. The same observation was also made with an approximately normal solution of ammonium beryllium fluoride. The details will be published later on. It is therefore assumed that in the aqueous solution of potassium beryllium fluoride or ammonium beryllium fluoride BeF_4^{--} -ion exists though partially dissociated into its constituents Be^{++} and $4F^-$. (A study of the dissociation constant of this complex ion is in progress.)

which are monoclinic and perfectly isomorphous with the well-known double sulphates of ammonium and those of magnesium family of elements studied by Locke. (*Amer. J. Sci.*, 1902, **27**, 455). With potassium beryllium fluoride the following isomorphous series of double salts have also been prepared.

In the above examples BeF_4'' has partially replaced SO_4'' . A third series of double salts have been prepared in which the SO_4 -ions have been completely replaced, *e.g.*, Am_2BeF_4 , NiBeF_4 , $6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ perfectly isomorphous with the aforesaid series. Further corroborative evidence of the analogy is afforded by the preparation of the fourth series, *viz.*, the alums, *e.g.*, $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$, Am_2BeF_4 , $24\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Moreover, a simple salt $\text{NiBeF}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ analogous to $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has also been prepared.

As it was expected that the two complex ions BeF_4'' and SO_4'' will show further chemical similarity in respect of various other salts soluble or insoluble, an attempt was made to prepare the fluoberyllates of the metals of the alkaline earths. Now, as the complex ion BeF_4 in aqueous solution is in mobile equilibrium with its ions,

$\text{BeF}_4'' \rightleftharpoons \text{Be}'' + 4\text{F}'$, we cannot use wet method to verify the above hypothesis. By fusing ammonium beryllium fluoride with anhydrous barium chloride at high temperature we have been able to isolate the compound BaBeF_4 which correspond to BaSO_4 and is equally insoluble in water and acids. It is thus evident that a close chemical analogy between two negative ions composed of elements belonging to widely different groups in the periodic table is possible. A detailed account of the investigations summarised above will appear in a series of subsequent communications.